

Cyclic voltammetric studies of some bis(phenanthrolines)copper(II) complexes

Krishna Srivastava*, Mala Kumari, Alpana Srivastava, Jagdish Prasad and K. B. Pandeya

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dr_krishna_s@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : The electrochemical properties of some bis(phenanthrolines)copper(II) complexes, $[\text{Cu}(\text{NN})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (NN denotes 1,10-phenanthroline (phen); 4,7-diphenyl-1,10-phenanthroline (bathophen); 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline (dmp) and 2,9-diphenyl-1,10-phenanthroline (dpp)) have been studied by cyclic voltammetry at a platinum working electrode in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and dimethyl formamide (DMF) containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as the supporting electrolyte. All these complexes display a quasireversible $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ redox couple. Both the electron-donating methyl groups and electron-withdrawing phenyl groups at the 2,9-positions of the phen ligand elevate the $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ redox potentials of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{dpp})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ complexes. The redox potentials of $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2]^{2+}$ are nearly 50 mV more positive than that of $[\text{Cu}(\text{dpp})_2]^{2+}$ in a given solvent. It is found that the $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ reduction potential (E_{pc}) as well as formal potential (E^0) for a given complex all shifted to more positive values in DMF as compared to that in DMSO.

Keywords : Copper(II), cyclic voltammetry, electrochemistry, phenanthrolines.

Bis(phenanthrolines)copper(I) complexes have received much attention for their being less expensive and environment friendly, interesting photochemical and photophysical properties¹⁻³, suitable for practical applications such as light harvesting for photovoltaic cells and as molecular sensors². It is believed that these pseudotetrahedral Cu^I complexes reorganise towards square-planar geometry in the excited state⁴.

In the present paper, we have studied the effect of chemical nature, the size and position of the substituents on the phenanthroline ring and also of the solvents (DMSO, DMF) on the electrochemical behaviour of bis(phenanthrolines)copper(II) complexes, $[\text{Cu}(\text{NN})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, where NN denotes phen, bathophen, dmp and dpp chelating ligands as shown below :

- | | |
|-----------------|---------------|
| R = R' = H, | L = phen |
| R = H, R' = Ph, | L = bathophen |
| R = Me, R' = H, | L = dmp |
| R = Ph, R' = H, | L = dpp |

Results and discussion

The electrochemical properties of bis(phenanthrolines)copper(II) complexes formed in DMSO/DMF solutions at a metal-to-ligand molar ratio of 1 : 3.5 (ligand = phen, bathophen, dmp and dpp) were preliminarily investigated at a platinum working electrode by cyclic voltammetry with scan rate (v) ranging from 25 to 300 mV s^{-1} . The cyclic voltammograms of $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2]^{2+}$ in DMSO/0.1 M TBAP are displayed in Fig. 1(a, b) at scan rate 50 mV s^{-1} and the electrochemical data for these complexes in DMSO and DMF are listed in Table 1. It has earlier been reported that $[\text{Cu}(\text{NN})_2]^{2+}$ complex species^{5,6} are formed in solution when the ligand-to-metal ratio is > 2.0 . All these Cu^{II} complexes reveal a single redox couple corresponding to the electrode process $[\text{CuL}_2]^{2+} \xrightleftharpoons[-e]{+e} [\text{CuL}_2]^+$ in both the media (DMSO/DMF/0.1 M TBAP). Controlled potential coulometry confirms that this reduction process involves one electron per molecule of the complex. Analysis of the CV data for the $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ couple with scan rates ranging from 25 to 300 mV s^{-1} showed the following characteristics. The anodic to cathodic peak current ratio ($I_{\text{pa}}/I_{\text{pc}}$) is ~ 1.0 , indicating that the electrode process involves a simple single-electron transfer reaction. The cathodic peak (E_{pc}) shifts cathodically with increasing scan rate (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of 1 mM solutions of $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (a) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (b) in DMSO/0.1 M TBAP at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} at Pt electrode.

Also, the value of $\Delta E_p (= E_{pa} - E_{pc})$ progressively increases with increasing scan rate. Both these observations are indicative of the heterogeneous quasireversible one-electron transfer process⁷. The plots of the cathodic peak current (I_{pc}) vs the square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) gives a straight line passing through origin, showing that the electrode process is diffusion-controlled⁷.

$\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ reduction potentials (E_{pc}) as well as the formal potential (E°) for a given complex all shifted to more positive values in DMF as compared to that in DMSO⁸ (Table 1). It must be mentioned that the reduction peak potentials (E_{pc}) of phen and bathophen Cu^{II} complexes differ slightly (by $\approx 30 \text{ mV}$) in a given solvent (Table 1), showing that the bulkier electron-withdrawing phenyl groups at 4- and 7-positions of the parent phen ligand have minor influence on $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ reduction potential of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{bathophen})_2]^{2+}$ complex. On the other hand, the magnitudes of redox potential of dmp and dpp complexes are much more positive as compared to those of phen and bathophen complexes (Table 1). This clearly shows that both the electron-donating methyl groups and electron-withdrawing phenyl groups at the 2- and 9-positions of the phen ligand greatly elevate the $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ redox potential⁹ of $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{dpp})_2]^{2+}$ complexes. One reason for the shift in potential is that bulky substituents in 2,9-positions limit the extent of D_2 flattening distortion (toward square-planar) preferred by the Cu^{II} complex due to steric clashes with the opposing ligands⁹. In addition the presence

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric data for $[\text{Cu}(\text{NN})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ in DMSO and DMF solutions containing 0.1 M TBAP at a Pt electrode

(NN) Ligand	Scan rate (mV s^{-1})	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	E° (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pa}/I_{pc}
DMSO solution :						
phen	25	+20	+90	+55	70	0.88
	150	+10	+100	+55	90	0.88
	300	-10	+110	+50	120	0.90
bathophen	25	+50	+130	+90	80	0.90
	150	+30	+170	+100	140	0.90
	300	+20	+180	+100	160	0.90
dmp	25	+630	+690	+660	60	1.0
	150	+600	+710	+655	110	1.0
	300	+580	+720	+650	140	1.0
dpp	25	+610	+670	+640	60	0.95
	150	+590	+650	+620	60	0.95
	300	+570	+670	+620	100	0.96
DMF solution :						
phen	25	+110	+200	+155	90	0.85
	150	+80	+210	+145	130	0.85
	300	+60	+230	+145	170	0.85
bathophen	25	+140	+230	+185	90	0.90
	150	+120	+250	+185	130	0.90
	300	+100	+260	+180	160	0.92
dmp	25	+670	+750	+710	80	1.0
	150	+640	+770	+705	130	1.0
	300	+620	+780	+700	160	1.0
dpp	25	+640	+710	+675	70	0.93
	150	+610	+720	+665	110	0.93
	300	+590	+730	+660	140	0.94

$$E^{\circ} = 1/2(E_{pa} + E_{pc}); \Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$$

of substituents inhibit the addition of a fifth ligand in the excited state. The magnitude of ΔE_p is larger in DMF as compared to that in DMSO for a given $[\text{Cu}(\text{NN})_2]^{2+}$ complex, indicating that the $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ redox process is less reversible⁷ in DMF.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were obtained from commercial sources. The solutions under investigation were freshly prepared by dissolving stoichiometric amounts (1 : 3.5 molar ratio) of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the ligands. The concentration of metal salt was kept constant (1 millimole) in each case.

Cyclic voltammetry was performed on a BAS model CV-1B instrument (USA) having an electrochemical cell

with a three electrode system. The working electrode was a platinum micro electrode (MF 2013), platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as a reference electrode ($E^0 = +0.242$ vs NHE). The cyclic voltammograms were recorded on X-Y recorder. All the cyclic voltammetry experiments were done in inert atmosphere achieved by purging the cell solution with pure nitrogen for about 20 min, and the inert atmosphere of nitrogen was also maintained over the cell solution during recording of the voltammograms. 0.1 M TBAP was used as the supporting electrolyte. All the experiments were performed at 30 ± 0.5 °C.

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